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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Jaya Vati is a Khalviya Rasayana described under Jwara Chikitsa in Rasendra Sara Sangraha, with additional references in Rasa Ratna Samucchaya, Ayurveda Prakasha, Rasendra Chintamani, Rasa Tarangini, and Rasa Sanketa Kalika, wherein the pharmaceutical method is comparable although the ingredients slightly vary. It is a Kashtoushadha containing 9 ingredients, with Shuddha Vatsanabha being one of them. **Materials and Methods:** The pharmaceutical preparation of Jaya Vati was as per the method mentioned in Rasendra Sara Sangraha, incorporating all ingredients. **Results:** Jaya Vati is indicated and explained as Yogavahi when administered with a suitable Anupana. Its therapeutical indications include types of Jwara, Prameha, Grahani, Bhagandara, Gulma, Kasa, Kushta, Shotha, Ashmari, Raktapitta. Jaya Vati can be widely used in Sarva Roga Chikitsa due to its Yogavahi Guna, which enhances the effectiveness of other Aushadhas administered alongside. **Discussion:** Despite the inclusion of the Visha Dravya Shuddha Vatsanabha, Jaya Vati is acclaimed for its remarkable therapeutic efficacy, attributable to the unique Guna–Karma of its ingredients. This paper highlights its classical pharmaceutical preparation and elucidates the therapeutic significance of Visha Dravya in Chikitsa.

KEYWORDS: Jaya Vati, Visha Dravya, Vatsanabha, Yogavahi.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda stands out as a science that recognises the remarkable principle that even a potent poison can become a powerful medicine when it is properly purified, processed, and administered. At the same time, a beneficial drug can turn harmful if used incorrectly. Reflecting this understanding, Acharyas have described Visha and Upavisha Dravyas in detail—covering their botanical features, methods of Shodhana (purification), therapeutic formulations, indications across various Vyadhis (Diseases), and the toxic effects that may arise from overdose or inadequate purification. Among these substances, Vatsanabha (*Aconitum ferox*) is considered one of the most significant plant origin Visha Dravya.

Jayavati is a lesser known but a distinct formulation amongst the various other Aushadha Yogas having Visha Dravya as an ingredient. It is explained under the Jwara

Chikitsa in the text, Rasendra Sara Sangraha.^[1] References of Jaya Vati are also found in Rasa Ratna Samucchaya, Ayurveda Prakasha, Rasendra Chintamani, Rasa Tarangini, and Rasa Sanketa Kalika.^[2] While the method of preparation is similar in these texts, the ingredients vary. It is a Kashtoushadha (Herbal medicine) containing 9 ingredients, with Shuddha Vatsanabha being one of them.

A detailed review revealed that Jayavati is currently unavailable in the market and is not produced by any existing Ayurvedic pharmaceutical company. In light of this gap, the formulation was systematically prepared in the Teaching Pharmacy of the Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana at Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research, Bengaluru. This paper highlights the pharmaceutical preparation of Jayavati and discusses its therapeutic relevance in Chikitsa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The reference for the present preparation was taken from Rasendra Sara Sangraha.

Details of the Practicals**PRACTICAL 01 – VATSANABHA SHODHANA**

a. **Ingredients** – the following are used for Shodhana of Vatsanabha as per the reference.^[3]

Table 1: Ingredients with Quantity for Vatsanabha Shodhana.

Ingredients	Quantity
Vatsanabha	10g
Gomutra	250ml

b. Method

1. Raw Vatsanabha Moola were taken, cleaned and weighed.
2. Required quantity of Gomutra was freshly collected.
3. Vatsanabha was tied in a piece of cloth, kept dipped in the Gomutra. This was exposed to the sunlight for three days.
4. Everyday fresh Gomutra was collected and replaced with previously used one.
5. After 3 days, Shodhita Vatsanabha were dried, made into powder and weighed.

c. Final Quantity obtained

Shodhita Vatsanabha – 14g

PRACTICAL 02 – JAYAVATI NIRMANA

a. **Ingredients** - the following are used for Jayavati preparation as per the reference.^[1]

Photo 1. Ingredients of Jayavati.

Photo 3. All Ingredients kept ready.

Table 2: Ingredients with Quantity for Jayavati Nirmana.

Ingredients	Quantity
Shuddha Vatsanabha	5g
Trikatu	5g
Musta	5g
Haridra	5g
Nimba Patra	5g
Vidanga	5g
Chhaga Mutra (Goat's Urine)	Quantity sufficient

b. METHOD

1. All the above ingredients were taken in the required quantities and made into a fine powder using Khalva Yantra.
2. The Churnas were mixed homogenously and added with sufficient quantity of Chhaga Mutra and subjected to Bhavana until Subhavita Lakshanas were obtained.
3. Seven Bhavanas were done and at the end of 7th Bhavana, the particle size had reduced, homogeneously mixed and turned into a smooth paste.
4. As per the reference, the medicine was rolled into Chanakabhavath Vati (size of Chanaka), dried in sunlight, weighed and stored in an air-tight container.

c. Final Quantity Obtained

Jayavati – 55g

Photo 2. Fine Churna of Ingredients.

Photo 4. Addition of Avi Mutra as Bhavana Dravya.

Photo 5. Bhavana done (7 times).

Photo 6. Jayavati Samples.

RESULTS

Table 3: Final Product with its yield.

Aushadha	Quantity
Jayavati	55g

Table 4: Organoleptic Characteristics of Jayavati.

Swaroop	Varna	Rasa	Gandha
Vati/ Tablet	Dark Brown	Tikta Pradhana	Mutra-Gandha

DISCUSSION

Guna-Karma of the Ingredients

Table 5 – Guna Karma of Dravyas.

Dravya	Guna-Karma
Vatsanabha ^[4]	Guna: Ruksha, Tikshna, Laghu, Vikasi, Sukshma, and Vyavayi Karma: Tridosha-Shamana, Jwaraghna, Shothaghna, Kasaghna, Vedanahara. Its Swedajanaka action promotes Dosha Nirharana
Trikatu ^[5]	Guna: Laghu, Ruksha, and Ushna Karma: Agni-Deepaka and Ruchikara, Medoghna, Mehaghna, Vishaghna, Aamavishahara, Gulmaghna
Musta ^[6]	Guna: Laghu and Ruksha Karma: Pachana, Grahi, Pitta-Kaphahara, Seetagrahi, Jwaraghna, Krimighna
Haridra ^[7]	Guna: Laghu and Ruksha Karma: Vishaghna, Varnya, Twachya Pramehahara, Shothaghna, Kandughna, Krimighna
Nimba ^[8]	Guna: Laghu and Ruksha Karma: Krimighna, Vishaghna, Kushtaghna, Vranahara, Netraya, Kasahara
Vidanga ^[9]	Guna: Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna. Karma: Krimighna, Dipana, Dhatu Poshana, Rasayana, Medohara, Kushtaghna
Avi Mutra	Guna: Ushna, Ruksha Karma: Shotha, Visha, Sulahara, Gulmaghna Pleehaghna, Shwasahara

Vyadhi-Anusara Jayavati Prayoga with specific Anupana^[10]

Table 6- List of Vyadhi-Anusara Specific Anupana.

Vyadhi	Anupana
Prameha	Administered along with Madhu and Lodra, Musta, Haritaki, and Katphala Kashaya, to support Kapha-Meda Shamana and regulation of Mutravaha Srotas.
Kushta	Advised with Gomutra, administered either internally or externally (E/A), to facilitate Dosha Shodhana and Twak Prasadana.
Ashmari, Mutrakrichha	Given with Tandulodaka as Anupana, aiding Mutravaha Srotas Shodhana.
Shotha, Pandu	Administered along with Ksheera, which helps mitigate Ushna and Tikshna effects while supporting Dhatu Poshana.
Kasa	Prescribed with Madhu, facilitating Kapha Vilayana and relief in Pranavaha Srotas disorders.
Vishama Jwara, Sarva Jwara	Administered with Ghrita, along with Trikatu Churna and Madhu, to enhance Agni, pacify Doshas.
Sannipata Jwara, Raktapitta	Advised with Maricha Churna, Madhu, and Chandana Kashaya, balancing Tridosha while providing Sheeta and Rakta-Prasadana effects.

Pittaja Jwara, Sheetaja Jwara	Administered with Go Ksheera, which helps pacify Pitta and stabilize Agni without aggravating Doshas.
Gulma	Prescribed along with Guda or Ushna Jala, supporting Vata-Kapha Shamana
Grahani	Administered with Takra, aiding Agni Deepana and Grahani Dosha correction.
Ratryandhya	Administered with Bhringaraja Swarasa, which supports Netra Prasadana

Yogavahitva^[11]: Yogavahitva refers to the property of certain substances by which they act as catalytic agents, carrying the Aushadhiya Gunas of co-administered Dravyas deep into the body without expressing their own dominant pharmacological action. A Yogavahi Dravya facilitates the targeted delivery of therapeutic attributes of an Aushadha into the Sapta Dhatus, thereby enhancing the overall therapeutic outcome.

Due to its Yogavahi nature, such a Dravya enhances the bioavailability of the administered formulation and promotes efficient tissue distribution. It increases the efficacy of drugs by enabling deeper penetration and precise action at the Dhatu level. Additionally, Yogavahi Dravyas help in minimizing or modulating adverse effects during the therapeutic process by optimizing drug action rather than intensifying dosage. This property also allows effective therapeutic delivery through non-parenteral routes, thereby circumventing the need for invasive modes of administration. Furthermore, Yogavahitva leads to a synergistic effect, wherein the combined action of the Yogavahi Dravya and the principal drug results in enhanced therapeutic potency greater than their individual effects.

Vatsanabha – A potent Mahavisha: classified as a Mahavisha in Ayurveda, exemplifies the concept of transforming a potent toxic substance into a therapeutic agent through appropriate Shodhana (purification) procedures. Raw Vatsanabha contains highly toxic diterpenoid alkaloids such as aconitine and pseudoaconitine, which upon processing are converted into less toxic derivatives like benzoylaconine and benzoylpseudoaconine, significantly reducing toxicity while retaining pharmacological activity. Phytoconstituents including flavonoids and terpenoids contribute to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and cardioprotective effects.^[12]

CONCLUSION

Jayavati embodies key Ayurvedic principles of Shodhana, Yogavahitva and Svayam Anupana, ensuring safety, effective absorption, and targeted therapeutic action. Its Yogavahi nature enhances deeper tissue penetration and potentiates drug efficacy, while its bioenhancer and biocatalyst properties support metabolic modulation. Additionally, Jayavati is pharmaceutically simple to prepare at the clinical level, requiring minimal processing, which facilitates standardization, fresh preparation, and practical use in routine Ayurvedic practice.

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